

Colorimetric Determination of Resorcinol in Pharmaceutical Preparations

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1-3 dihydroxybenzene commercially known as resorcinol is a fungicide. It is used to cure some skin diseases due to its antifungal and antibacterial activity. Resorcinol is formulated in pharmaceutical preparations in the form of ointments, lotions and creams for external application. Literature survey reveals many colorimetric and titrimetric methods of estimation of resorcinol.

The official method¹ involves iodometric titration. Colorimetric methods using Felin-Denis reagent², 4-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde³, vanadates of 8-hydroxyquinoline⁴ are lengthy as complete colour development takes about 30 minutes. Colour formation with iron salts⁵ and 3, 5-dibromo *p*-benzoquinonechlorimine⁶ are non-specific as all the phenolic compounds develop colours with these reagents. We have observed that, resorcinol forms violet colouration with *p*-aminophenol (PAP) in alkaline medium. This colour reaction was studied and standard procedure for estimation of resorcinol was developed.

It was found that this procedure requires only 5 minutes for complete colour development and it does not involve any special treatment as required in the other published methods²⁻⁵.

Experimental

All chemicals and solvents used were of A.R. grade.

Standard solution of resorcinol :

A standard solution of resorcinol of concentration 1 mg/ml was prepared in distilled water and working standard solution of concentration 10 μ g/ml was prepared from this stock solution.

Sample solution of resorcinol :

The sample solution of concentration 10 μ g/ml of resorcinol was prepared in distilled water.

Assay procedure :

2 ml of each standard and sample were taken separately in 10 ml test tubes and 2 ml of 1 *M* NaOH and 1.4 ml of the reagent were added. The volume of the mixture was adjusted to the mark with distilled water. After 5 minutes the absorbance was noted at 585 nm against the reagent blank.

Table 1 gives the comparative data of the application of the proposed method in the estimation of resorcinol in the commercial pharmaceutical products.

Results and Discussion

The proposed method is simple, fast and accurate. The results obtained are reproducible and compare satisfactorily with those obtained from the official method. Commonly used bases in creams, lotions and ointments like lanolin, kaolin, white paraffin base etc. produce no difficulty in estimation. Other commonly formulated ingredients like cetrimide, boric acid, iodochlorohydroxyquinoline etc. do not interfere. The percentage recovery is almost 100.

TABLE—1

Product	Resorcinol present.	Resorcinol found.	Percentage recovery.	Resorcinol found by official method ¹
Ointment-A (Bismuth Resorcin Compound)	1.75 %	1.75 %	99.80	1.80 %
Cream-A (Resorcinol.)	3 %	2.98 %	99.78	2.90%
Lotion-A (Resorcinol.)	3 %	3.01 %	100.06	2.90%

Reagent solution :

0.04 percent solution of PAP was prepared by dissolving 40 mg of PAP in 100 ml ethanol.

Alkali solution :

1 *M* NaOH was prepared in distilled water.

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